

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF HMPA COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II) CARBOXYLATES

Sl no.	Compd.	M. p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			λ_{max} nm	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Cu	C	H		
1.	Cu(benzoate) ₂ .HMPA	238*	12.89 (13.11)	49.38 (49.53)	5.59 (5.77)	700 ^a	1.52
2.	Cu(<i>o</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	226	12.17 (12.39)	51.26 (51.51)	6.12 (6.24)	680 ^b	1.59
3.	Cu(<i>m</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	*	12.20 (12.39)	51.29 (51.51)	6.19 (6.24)	690 ^b	1.63
4.	Cu(<i>p</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	247	12.27 (12.39)	51.30 (51.51)	6.09 (6.24)	682 ^a	1.46
5.	Cu(<i>o</i> -chlorobenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	214	11.27 (11.47)	43.17 (43.36)	4.48 (4.69)	685 ^a	1.60
6.	Cu(<i>m</i> -chlorobenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	249	11.39 (11.47)	43.19 (43.36)	4.50 (4.69)	680 ^b	1.56
7.	Cu(<i>p</i> -methoxybenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	241	11.40 (11.66)	48.27 (48.48)	5.68 (5.87)	675 ^a	1.50
8.	Cu(<i>m</i> -nitrobenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	248	10.92 (11.06)	41.56 (41.77)	4.41 (4.52)	685 ^a	1.48
9.	Cu(monochloroacetate) ₂ .HMPA	188	14.32 (14.79)	27.68 (27.93)	5.01 (5.12)	690 ^a 716 ^b	1.56
10.	Cu(dichloroacetate) ₂ .HMPA	202*	12.58 (12.74)	23.88 (24.07)	3.88 (4.01)	800 ^a 728 ^b	1.63

*Decomposes. ^aDiffuse reflectance spectra. ^bIn CHCl₃.

frequency difference between the asymmetric and symmetric carboxylate stretches lies in the range 230-250 cm⁻¹ with the exception of the complex of copper(II) dichloroacetate where this separation is 286 cm⁻¹. These values are appreciably higher than those found in the corresponding parent copper(II) carboxylates and are similar to those of binuclear complexes of copper(II) arylcarboxylates and chloroacetates with oxygen donors¹⁴ suggesting a usual dimeric carboxylate bridged structure for these complexes.

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Studies on some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Pyrrolidonates with some Nitrogen Donors

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A large number of transition metal complexes with various heterocyclic Schiff bases and oximes have been reported from this laboratory¹⁻⁵. The present paper reports the studies on some mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} pyrrolidonates with different amines, such as aniline piperidine, α -picoline, pyridine (L), ethylenediamine, tetramethylethylenediamine (L') and diethylenetriamine or triethylenetetraamine (L'').

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
			M	C	H	N		
1.	[Cu(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₇ N) ₂]	Dark brown	15.00 (15.21)	58.13 (57.47)	6.13 (6.22)	12.89 (13.41)	2.08	2.29
2.	[Cu(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₁₁ N) ₂]	Light green	16.10 (15.82)	52.95 (53.79)	10.40 (10.55)	13.48 (13.94)	1.90	1.84
3.	[Cu(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₇ NO) ₂]	Brown	15.10 (15.66)	48.00 (47.34)	6.50 (6.90)	13.50 (13.80)	2.80	1.90
4.	[Cu(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₁₁ N) ₂]	Dark green	18.50 (18.82)	50.10 (49.77)	8.12 (8.29)	16.23 (16.59)	Insol	2.08
5.	Cu(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₇ NO)	Brown	20.91 (21.72)	41.76 (41.02)	6.28 (6.49)	14.16 (14.35)	Insol	1.96
6.	[Ni(C ₄ N ₆ N') ₂ (C ₆ H ₇ N) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Dark brown	13.65 (13.95)	50.93 (51.34)	6.10 (6.18)	13.12 (13.31)	5.60	3.25
7.	[Ni(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₁₁ N) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Light pink	13.20 (13.56)	50.40 (49.92)	7.39 (7.85)	12.52 (12.94)	Insol	3.43
8.	[Ni(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₇ N) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellowish green	13.41 (13.08)	52.98 (53.48)	6.59 (6.68)	12.25 (12.48)	3.50	3.41
9.	[Ni(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	13.20 (13.43)	33.40 (32.97)	7.21 (7.32)	11.99 (12.82)	Insol	2.97
10.	[Ni(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₇ NO)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Pink	17.85 (18.18)	38.10 (37.07)	6.91 (7.10)	11.85 (12.97)	4.35	3.23
11.	[Ni(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₁₁ N) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Light pink	15.61 (15.91)	33.01 (32.54)	8.50 (8.67)	14.98 (15.18)	Insol	3.48
12.	[Ni(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₁₁ N) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	Pink	16.13 (16.87)	41.83 (41.41)	7.59 (7.76)	20.00 (20.13)	5.60	2.88
13.	[Ni(C ₄ H ₆ NO) ₂ (C ₆ H ₁₁ N ₄)]	Pinkish	15.54 (15.74)	44.98 (45.07)	7.95 (8.04)	21.95 (22.53)	6.50	3.06

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND LIGAND PARAMETER OF Ni²⁺ COMPLEXES

Obs. V ₂ kK	Obs. V ₁ kK	Obs. V ₁ kK	Obs. Dq cm ⁻¹	B cm ⁻¹	β	V ₂ /V ₁	Calcd. V ₂ kK	Calcd. V ₁ kK
27.60	16.16	10.87	1043	944	0.875	1.47	19.57	30.00
	14.09	10.00						
26.30	15.15	9.61	961	895	0.828	1.57	17.30	28.50
	13.50							
27.01	14.70	10.20	1020	881	0.817	1.40	18.35	29.25
	13.50							
26.67	14.29	9.73	973	894	0.828	1.51	15.80	27.52
	13.33							
24.40	16.13	9.80	980	935	0.865	1.46	17.64	28.77
	13.70							
26.17	14.71	10.09	1009	964	0.893	1.53	17.01	28.34
	16.13							
25.00	17.86	10.42	1042	981	0.908	—	17.30	28.51
	13.52							
26.67	16.94	10.00	1049	1035	0.962	1.58	18.17	29.12
	14.40	10.99						

The hitherto unknown Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ pyrrolidones have been obtained by treating sodium pyrrolidonate with an aqueous solution of corresponding metal(II) sulphate and possess the formulae Cu(C₄H₆NO)₂·2H₂O and Ni(C₄H₆NO)₂·4H₂O. The complexes were then prepared by suspending a known amount of these salts (1 mol) in methanol and adding to it the amine (1 mol). The solution was refluxed for 6 h and the complexes were crystallised out by repeated treatment with petroleum ether (b.p 60–80°). The complexes are sparingly soluble in methanol, nitrobenzene and DMF, and start decomposing on heating and hence their melting points could not be determined. These have been characterised using various physicochemical

methods as described. The metal was estimated using standard methods. The microanalytical estimation of C, H and N as well as the infrared spectra were recorded at C. D. R. I., Lucknow. The magnetic and electronic spectral measurements were made at Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis show the complexes to possess the formula [Cu(C₄H₆ON)₂(L')(H₂O)₂], [Ni(C₄H₆ON)₂(dien)(H₂O)], [Ni(C₄H₆ON)₂(trien)], where, C₄H₆ON = uninegative pyrrolidonate ion; L = aniline, piperidine, pyridine, α -picoline, morpholine; L' = ethanolamine, tetra-

methylethylenediamine, dien = diethylenetriamine and trien = triethylenetetraamine.

Low conductance of the complexes in nitrobenzene corresponds to their non-electrolytic nature as indicated by the formula above and suggests that the deprotonation of the NH group of free 2-pyrrolidone has occurred and it has been converted into its uninegative ion, which is capable of acting as a bidentate ligand coordinating through CO and NH groups. However, keeping in view the nature of the ligands used in the study, it is not possible for the ion to act as a bidentate ligand and hence it is suggested that it should have only as a monodentate ligand thus conferring the usual coordination numbers of four on the Cu^{2+} and six on Ni ions. The site of its coordination is the CO group, since in the ir spectra a sharp band appears at 1690 cm^{-1} (CO) stretch, which in free ketone is seen at 1725 cm^{-1} (Refs. 6, 7). The coordination of amines is indicated by the shifts of their relevant ir bands⁸⁻¹². The planar and octahedral geometries of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes are confirmed by their magnetic and electronic data.

The Cu^{2+} complexes are paramagnetic with the magnetic moment around 1.90 B.M. The appearance of a d-d band at 16.00 kK accompanied by two shoulders at 12.00 and 10.50 kK, assignable as ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$, ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{2g}$ transitions respectively, is indicative of planar stereochemistry. The values of μ_{eff} for Ni^{2+} complexes lie in the range 2.97-3.20 B.M. suggesting octahedral stereochemistry. These complexes show three comparatively weak bands at 23.00, 17.50 and 9.50 kK which correspond to the three idealised (O_h symmetry) transitions such as ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3), ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) band, ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$ (ν_1), respectively. The ν_2 as well as ν_3 transitions are found to be broken down in two components which is due to the departure of the symmetry towards pseudooctahedral. The values of the ligand field parameters have been calculated using the well known equation¹³, and it is found that the Dq values for complexes of ligands L are somewhat lower than those L' or L'' which correlates well with the positions of these ligands in spectrochemical series. The β values suggest the presence of sufficient amount of covalent character on the metal-ligand band.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Nickel(II), Copper(II), Palladium(II) and Platinum(II) with Pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and Acetylacetone

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IN continuation of our earlier work¹ on mixed ligand complexes, we now report a slightly different type of mixed ligand complexes of the type described below.

Experimental

[MLL'], type of complexes (where, M = Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} or Pt^{2+} ; L = pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde; and L' = acetylacetone) were prepared by adding pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and acetylacetone to the metal acetate solution in 1:1:1 ratio. The coloured solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from methanol. The solid on reaction with an excess of ammonia or alkylamines gave [MLL'A] type complexes (where, A = ammonia or alkylamine molecule) which on refluxing with ethanolamine on a water-bath for 2-3 h gave [MLE.H₂O] type complexes (where, E = ethanolamine). The complexes were recrystallised from methanol.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes gave satisfactory elemental analyses. On analysis [MLE.H₂O] type complexes, in addition, indicated the presence of a water molecule per molecule of the complex. These compounds are soluble in common organic solvents. Their negligibly small molar conductance values ($3.2\text{-}7.2\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$) suggest them to be non-electrolytic in nature. The Ni^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+} complexes are found diamagnetic while Cu^{2+} complexes are paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 1.88$ B.M.) at room temperature.